

ROCK SAMPLES

Make your
research

FAIR

MINISTERIO
DE CIENCIA, INNOVACIÓN
Y UNIVERSIDADES

AGENCIA
ESTATAL DE
INVESTIGACIÓN

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Take GPS position of
the samples and a
photo of the outcrop.

Record who, when,
and how the samples
were taken.

Label the samples with a
pre-established unique
identification code.

Photograph the samples with an accompanying
label displaying their identification code, size
scale, and color reference.

Assign an IGSN (International Generic Sample Number)
to each sample: <https://ev.igsn.org> o
<https://www.geosamples.org>

Assign a DOI to the sample
collection.

Cite the DOI of the sample
collection and the individual
IGSNs in related publications.

FIELDWORK

LABORATORY

MAKE YOUR RESEARCH

F

Findable

Easily findable data, with unique identifiers and detailed, accessible metadata.

A

Accessible

Data and metadata hosted in a reliable repository with dual human-machine accessibility.

I

Interoperable

Interoperable data and metadata compatible with other tools and data sources, using common standards and shared languages.

R

Reusable

Comprehensively documented data with explicit usage licenses enabling cross-domain application.